

1 **Supplementary Materials for: Aiswarya Mukundan Nair, Helen Piontkivska, “SARS-**
2 **CoV-2 infection induced alterations in ADAR editing patterns differ between**
3 **patients who developed critical compared to non-critical COVID-19”**

4
5 Supplementary materials and code are shared at
6 https://github.com/RNAdetective/Editing_in_critical-non-critical-COVID-19
7

8 **List of supplementary tables and figures:**

9
10 (see Supplementary Figures below)

11
12 **Supplemental Figure 1.** PCA plot of top 500 differentially expressed genes. PC1 clearly
13 separated critical from non-critical patients.

14 **Supplemental Figure 2. Difference in ADAR editing between critical and non-critical**

15 **patients** (A) Average number of ADAR edits between critical and non-critical patients.

16 (B) Region wise distribution of uniquely edited sites within non-critical patients. inset

17 plots show different types of substitutions within exonic regions. (C) Region wise

18 distribution of uniquely edited sites within critical patients. inset plots show different

19 types of substitutions within exonic regions. (D) Screenshot of interactive 3D viewer

20 showing interatomic interactions of the wildtype residue (S) at position 164 in exon 3 in

21 HLA-DRB5 gene carrying non-synonymous substitution in non-critical patients. (E)

22 Screenshot of interactive 3D viewer showing interatomic interactions of the wildtype

23 residue (H) at position 292 in exon 7 in DHRSX gene carrying non-synonymous

24 substitution in critical patients.

25 **Supplemental Figure 3.** Genomic distribution of differentially edited sites. Highest

26 number of differentially edited sites mapped to introns followed by 3'UTR, exonic

27 region also contains a missense edit.

28
29 (see Supplementary Tables as separate XLSX files)

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31 **Supp_Table_1.xlsx**

32
33 Supplemental_Table_1A: DESeq2 differential gene expression analysis results
34 comparing Critical COVID-19 samples to Non-critical COVID-19 samples, filtered for
35 $\log_2\text{Fold Change} \geq |0.58|$ (Fold Change > 1.5) and an adjusted P value < 0.05
36

37 Supplemental_Table_1B: DESeq2 differential gene expression analysis, genes
38 upregulated in Critical COVID-19 samples compared to Non-critical COVID-19
39 samples, filtered for $\log_2\text{Fold Change} \geq 0.58$ (Fold Change > 1.5) and an adjusted P
40 value < 0.05
41

42 Supplemental_Table_1C: DESeq2 differential gene expression analysis, genes
43 downregulated in Critical COVID-19 samples compared to Non-critical COVID-19
44 samples, filtered for log2Fold Change ≤ -0.58 (Fold Change > 1.5) and an adjusted P
45 value < 0.05
46

47 Supplemental_Table_1D: Gene Set Enrichment Analysis of Reactome pathways
48 enriched among differentially expressed genes ordered by Nominal Enrichment Score
49 (NES) and p-adj < 0.05
50

51 Supplemental_Table_1E: Gene Set Enrichment Analysis of GO-BP enriched among
52 differentially expressed genes, ordered by Nominal Enrichment Score (NES) and p-adj
53 < 0.05
54

55 Supplemental_Table_1F: DESeq2 differential gene expression analysis results
56 comparing Critical COVID-19 samples to Non-critical COVID-19 samples before
57 applying filters of \log_2 Fold Change $\geq |0.58|$ (Fold Change > 1.5) and an adjusted P
58 value < 0.05
59

60 Supplemental_Table_1G: Transcript level ADAR expression as DESeq2 normalized
61 counts. Isoform transcript Ids were retrieved from Ensembl
62

63 Supplemental_Table_1H: Transcript level ADAR expression data from DESeq2
64

65 **Supp_Table_2.xlsx**
66

67 Supplemental_Table_2A: Sample wise total number of different substitution types,
68 including A-to-G and T-to-C substitutions
69

70 Supplemental_Table_2B: Average region-wise number of ADAR editing sites within
71 each patient group
72

73 Supplemental_Table_2C: Editing sites and corresponding genes unique edited in
74 patients with non-critical COVID-19
75

76 Supplemental_Table_2D: Editing sites and corresponding genes unique edited in
77 patients with critical COVID-19
78

79 Supplemental_Table_2E: GO-BP overrepresentation analysis of uniquely edited genes
80

81 Supplemental_Table_2F: Reactome pathway overrepresentation analysis of uniquely
82 edited genes
83

84 **Supp_Table_3.xlsx**

85

86 Supplemental_Table_3A: List of identified high confidence sites annotated with snpEff

87

88 Supplemental_Table_3B: High confidence sites present in REDI portal

89

90 Supplemental_Table_3C: High confidence sites not-present in REDI portal/ Novel sites

91

92 Supplemental_Table_3D: High confidence ADAR sites differentially edited between
93 critical compared to non-critical patients

94

95 Supplemental_Table_3E: GSEA results of differentially edited sites using Reactome

96

97 **Supp_Table_4.xlsx**

98

99 Supplemental_Table_4: Features/edited coordinates with AUC>0.75

100

101 **Supp_Table_5.xlsx**

102

103 Supplemental_Table_5: Metrics of analyzed RNA-seq data from Bioproject
104 PRJNA722046; GSE172114 (Carapito et al.,2022).

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108

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